

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Implementation of the policy of equalizing the position of administrator into functional in Gorontalo City Government

Zul Ilham Zakaria *, Zuchri Abdussamad and Sukarman Kamuli

Master of Public Administration Postgraduate Study Program, Gorontalo State University, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 22(01), 1970–1975

Publication history: Received on 11 March 2024; revised on 17 April 2024; accepted on 20 April 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.22.1.1203>

Abstract

The implementation of PermenPAN-RB policy number 17 of 2021 concerning the equalization of administrative positions into functional positions has been implemented by the Gorontalo City Government. This study aims to determine how the implementation of this policy and the factors that determine the success of policy implementation within the Gorontalo City Government. This research is a qualitative descriptive with research locations at the Gorontalo City Staffing, Education and Training Agency (BKPP) and the Organization and Governance Section of the Gorontalo City Regional Secretariat from September to November 2023. Data collection techniques in the form of observation, interviews and documentation. The results of the study found that policy implementation has been running at the planning, supervision and policy evaluation stages, but has not been optimal at the policy implementation stage. The determining factors for the success of policy implementation based on aspects of communication, resources, disposition (attitude of implementers) and bureaucratic structure are still not optimal. The communication aspect has not been effective both in the aspects of transmission, clarity and consistency. The resource aspect has not been effective on human resources, budget resources, equipment resources. The disposition/attitude aspect of the executor has been effective. The aspect of bureaucratic structure is influenced by other factors, namely communication factors, making this factor less efficient.

Keywords: Policy implementation; Equalization of positions; Gorontalo City

1. Introduction

Bureaucratic reform is a policy that is being carried out by the government to achieve good governance. One form of bureaucratic reform is the simplification of the bureaucratic system by replacing certain structural positions with functional positions. This policy is contained in the *merit system* in accordance with Ministerial Regulation Number 40 of 2018 concerning merit system guidelines. Derivatives of this policy include Government Regulation (PP) number 17 of 2020 concerning Amendments to PP number 11 of 2017 concerning civil servant management, PermenPAN-RB number 13 of 2019 concerning the proposal, determination, and development of functional positions of civil servants, PermenPAN RB number 17 of 2021 concerning equalization of administrative positions into functional positions which revoked Minister of PAN RB Number 28 of 2019. PermenPAN-RB is expected to be a simplification of bureaucracy to improve the efficiency and performance of civil servants and make the implementation of bureaucracy faster and more dynamic in decision making. PermenPAN-RB number 25 of 2021 concerning bureaucratic simplification is divided into three parts, namely organizational transformation, apparatus human resources and work systems. The enactment of PAN RB Regulation number 17 of 2021 has an impact on bureaucratic work systems and mechanisms, especially for local governments. One of them is the implementation of the Minister of PAN RB Number 17 of 2021 article 34 paragraph 1 and article 34 paragraph 2 so that Regional Governments are obliged to make appointments and inauguration of equalization into functional positions and be carried out no later than December 31, 2021.

* Corresponding author: Zul Ilham Zakaria.

Gorontalo City Government as one of the extensions of the Central Government has implemented PermenPAN-RB policy number 28 of 2019 through equalization and inauguration of administrative positions into functional positions at the end of 2021 in 26 Agencies/SKPD. Data obtained from administrative positions are equated into functional positions from 26 SKPD in the Gorontalo City government, as many as 261 functional positions with 253 officials have been appointed within the Gorontalo City government. In accordance with preliminary observations made by researchers that 253 officials appointed are Echelon IV supervisory administrative officials who have been equated to young expert functional officials.

The implementation of the policy of equalizing administrative positions to functional positions within the Gorontalo City Regional Government has many challenges that will be faced including: 1) the work system of functional positions that are very different from structural positions, 2) the task of coordinating functions and managing activities for equalization functional officials, where Associate Expert Functional Officers are assigned as Coordinators and Young Expert Functional Officers are assigned as Sub coordinator. 3) The duties of the main function (Tupoksi) of functional positions that are not the same as the previous administrative positions. 4) Challenges of career development of functional officials through equalization pathways. 5) there is no credit score assessment agency in Gorontalo Province. The implementation of the equalization policy requires a systematic strategy to achieve a more dynamic and professional bureaucracy. The achievement strategy focuses on aspects of planning, implementation, and evaluation.

The results of the study of Fitrianingrum *et al.* (2020) found that the implementation of the bureaucratic simplification process can ideally be done by first structuring the organizational structure and work procedures (SOTK) which is then followed by a position balancing process. However, because SOTK setup requires a long and time-consuming process, the two processes can be carried out in parallel. Meanwhile, Edward in Dalimunthe & Susilawati (2022) mentions four factors that affect the implementation of public policies, namely communication, resources, disposition (attitude of implementers) and bureaucratic structure.

This study aims to determine how the implementation of the policy of equalizing the position of administrator into functional positions, as well as the factors that determine the success of the implementation of the policy within the Gorontalo City Government

2. Method

This type of research is descriptive research with a qualitative approach with the location of the research, namely at the Gorontalo City Staffing, Education and Training Agency (BKPP) and the Gorontalo City Organization and Governance Section during September to November 2023. Data collection techniques in the form of observation, interviews, and documentation. Observations and interviews were conducted on several informants consisting of the Head of the Gorontalo City BKPP, the Head of the Gorontalo City Organization Section, the Head of the Gorontalo City BKPP Mutation Division, the Human Resources Analysis at the Gorontalo City Organization Section and 11 Gorontalo City Government Functional Officials.

The data analysis technique is Miles and Huberman's interactive model analysis, which is qualitative data analysis that is carried out interactively and continues to the end so that the data becomes saturated. Some stages in this technique are data reduction, data presentation, conclusion drawing and checking the validity of data.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Implementation of equalization policy in Gorontalo City Government

3.1.1. Planning

Based on the results of interviews from several informants and observations made, it is known that the planning process is based on Circular Letters from the Ministry of PAN-RB Number 384, 390 and 391 of 2019 which contain strategic steps to simplify bureaucracy. Based on this circular, the organizational section of the Regional Secretariat made a circular to each SKPD to identify administrative positions in SKPD by personnel officials in each SKPD. Position identification is carried out by looking at the Tupoksi of each supervisory officer and comparing it with the Tupoksi of Functional positions in accordance with the duties and positions of supervisors owned. The identification process is carried out with supervisory officials who will be equated to functional positions for each SKPD. The Organization Section of the Regional Secretariat of the Gorontalo City Government then mapped the affected positions and administrative officials based on the results of the position identification carried out. The Organization Bureau together

with the Head of the Civil Service Sub-Division of each SKPD then mapped the functional positions that could be occupied by affected officials. The organizational bureau then collaborated with the Gorontalo City BKPP to map and calculate the income of existing officials by comparing the income before and after equalization from administrative positions to proposed functional positions. In summary, the explanation can be seen in Figure 1

Figure 1 Scheme in Planning for the implementation of the policy of equalizing administrative positions into Functional Positions in Gorontalo City Government

3.1.2. Implementation

The results of interviews and observations conducted found that the application of this policy was carried out on supervisory / echelon IV officials who were equated to young expert functional officials. The stages of policy implementation consist of several stages, namely the stage of proposal, review, validation, letters of recommendation, appointment, and inauguration. The Organization Section, as the person in charge of the policy in collaboration with the Gorontalo City BKPP has an important role in the implementation of this policy. The Gorontalo City Government proposed a position equalization document through the provincial government to the ministry of state apparatus empowerment and bureaucratic reform (KemenPAN-RB) regarding an organizational simplification plan containing plans for what functional positions would later be accommodated in the type of duties of the Local Government organization.

The Ministry of PAN-RB will carry out a process of verification, validation, coordination, and discussion of proposals to obtain technical considerations in the issuance of recommendation letters for consideration of simplifying the organizational structure of regional apparatus within the Gorontalo City Regional Government. Letters of recommendation can be used by local governments as guidelines in making appointments and inaugurations of these functional officials. The Gorontalo City Government appointed and inaugurated 261 functional officials on December 31, 2021. The explanation of the implementation stage above can be illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Steps to implement the policy of equalizing administrative positions into functional positions in the Gorontalo City government.

3.1.3. Monitoring and Evaluation

The results of interviews and observations found that the monitoring and evaluation stage of this policy was carried out by the Organizational Section of the Gorontalo City Regional Secretariat together with the Gorontalo City BKPP, namely through the preparation of Position Analysis (ANJAB) and Workload Analysis (ABK) after equalization of positions. The two agencies involve all Heads of Personnel Sub-Divisions of each SKPD to carry out Job Analysis Evaluation (EVJAB) and Workload Analysis (ABK) after the implementation of this policy. This activity is carried out starting from the stage of collecting, recording, processing and compiling position data to obtain information on work effectiveness and efficiency based on work volume to the composition of names and levels of high leadership positions, administrative positions and functional positions organizational unit structure from the lowest level to the highest based on PermenPAN-RB Number 1 of 2020 concerning Guidelines for Position Analysis and Workload Analysis. The Gorontalo City Government has appointed and inaugurated 261 functional officials who have been transferred to functional positions on December 31, 2021.

Problems arising from the impact of the implementation of policies include functional positions that are not in accordance with previous structural positions, equalized functional officials who do not understand the guidelines in carrying out functional positions. To accommodate this problem, the Minister of Home Affairs issued letter Number 800/2237/OTDA regarding the follow-up process of simplifying bureaucracy in provincial and regency/city local governments. In this case, the Gorontalo City Government has proposed adjusting the nomenclature of certain functional positions because of equalizing positions with 38 positions that have been given recommendations and approved by the Ministry of PAN

3.2. Factors that determine the success of policy implementation at Gorontalo City Government

Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted found that the communication factor in the implementation of this policy has not been effective. This can be seen from the lack of socialization carried out related to policies. The results of the interview found that socialization carried out to officials affected by this policy was only carried out once in 2022 at the BKPP Office Hall in Gorontalo City. This makes the implementation of the equalization policy less optimal because policy communication is not only conveyed to policy implementers, but also should reach the officials affected by this policy, namely functional officials

Findings in the field on resource factors have not been fully effective. This can be seen from human resources, budget resources, equipment resources. The results of the equalization carried out by the Gorontalo City Government still found several problems, including those related to the discrepancy in human resource competence to functional positions. This condition is the impact of not conducting competency tests in the equalization process.

The results of observations on the attitude factors of implementers show that the implementation of equalization policies has been effective. This can be seen from the willingness to implement policies and the ability to implement policies. The Gorontalo city government has equalized administrative positions in supervisory officials which are equated into functional positions from 26 SKPD in the Gorontalo City government, as many as 261 functional positions.

The results of observations and interviews found that the organizational structure factor in the implementation of this policy has not been effective. This can be seen from the various questions that arise, especially by the affected officials, whether this equalization of positions is able to encourage the professionalism of civil servants or just a mere normative change. In addition, this policy when viewed from the division of authority, relationships between organizational units and function tasks that have not experienced significant changes after the equalization policy, this will certainly have an impact on measuring the improvement of public services before and after the equalization policy.

4. Conclusion

Based on the discussion as well as facts and information encountered in the field, conclusions can be drawn including:

The implementation of the policy of equalizing administrative positions into functional positions of the State Civil Apparatus at the Gorontalo City Government has been going well at the planning, supervision, and policy evaluation stages, but has not been optimal at the policy implementation stage.

The determining factors for the success of policy implementation based on aspects of communication, resources, disposition (attitude of implementers) and bureaucratic structure are still not optimal. The communication aspect has not been effective both from transmission, clarity, and consistency. The resource aspect has not been effective in terms of human resources, budget resources, equipment resources. The disposition/attitude aspect of the executor has been effective. The aspect of bureaucratic structure is influenced by other factors, namely communication factors, making this factor less efficient.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Andrianus Lian, Handayani, A. M. D., Ananda Anggun Dea, Astuty Dessy, & Andyana. (2022). Management of demand and production capacity at Grace Florist MSMEs in Batam. *Journal of Scientific Horizons*, 67–72.
- [2] Aneta, A. (2012). The development of the theory of state administration.
- [3] Arif, E., & Dewi, R. S. (2022). Culture of Verbal and Nonverbal Family Communication in Rural Areas: A Case Study in Agam District, West Sumatra Province. *Journal of Anthropology: Socio-Cultural Issues*, 24(2), 204. <https://doi.org/10.25077/jantro.v24.n2.p204-212.2022>
- [4] Basri, H., Rasyid Ridla, M., & Wahed, A. (2014). English Vocabulary Learning Strategy of TBI STAIN Pamekasan Students.
- [5] Basuki, J. (2021). Challenges of Public Administration Science: A New Paradigm of State Apparatus Leadership. *Public Inspiration: Journal of Public Administration*, 6(2), 160–181. <https://doi.org/10.22225/pi.6.2.2021.160-181>
- [6] Dalimunthe, Y. P., & Susilawati. (2022). The implementation of the covid 19 vaccination policy in Medan City uses the theory of Edward III. *Scientific Journal of HealthState Islamic University of North Sumatra*, 1, 59–64.
- [7] Dewi Ni Luh Yulyana. (2019). Dynamics of Collaborative Governance in Public Policy Studies. *Scientific Journal of Social Dynamics*, 3, 200–210. <https://journal.undiknas.ac.id>
- [8] Ervanto, R. A., Tahir, I., & Lambelanova, R. (2022). Implementation of Manpower Policy in Bekasi Regency. 1(2), 338–355. <https://bekasisociety.com/2020/12/16/>

- [9] Igirisa, I., Sartika, D., Ilato, R., & Kamuli, S. (2022). *British Journal of Philosophy, Sociology and History Implementation of Local Management Information System (SIMDA) in Quality Improvement of Financial Report of Buol Regencial Government*. <https://doi.org/10.32996/bjps>
- [10] Merry Natalia, B., Mardiyono, & Said, A. (2014). Implementation of the Prima Drinking Water Zone (Zamp) Program to Meet Community Drinking Water Needs (Study on PDAM Malang City). In JAP (Vol. 2, Issue 1).
- [11] Panca Timur Widya, Fauzi Amin, Yakub, & Satyawati Tara. (2022). Implementation of equalization of administrative positions of education personnel to functional positions at Surabaya State University. *Journal of Educational Management Dynamics*, 07, 39–47. <https://doi.org/10.26740/jdmp.v4n1.p1-10>
- [12] Pasolong, H. (2010). *Theory of Public Administration*. Second printing. Bandung: Alfabeta, CV., 1–214.
- [13] Rifa Aprilia, N., Rina Herawati, A., & Hariani, D. (2022). Implementation of Child Protection Policy from Violence at the East Semarang Sub-District Integrated Service Center (PPTK).
- [14] Roziqin, A., Mas'udi, S. Y. F., & Sihidi, I. T. (2021). An analysis of Indonesian government policies against COVID-19. *Public Administration and Policy*, 24(1), 92–107. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PAP-08-2020-0039>
- [15] Samosir Paramitha, Achmad Mansyur, & sinurat marja. (2022). Analysis of the implementation of the equalization policy for certain functional positions at the Regional Staffing, Education and Training Agency of Kupang City, East Nusa Tenggara Province. In *Management Studies and Entrepreneurship Journal* (Vol. 3, Issue 6). <http://journal.yrpiiku.com/index.php/msej>
- [16] Saputro, G. E., & Prakoso, L. Y. (2021). Implementation of Economic Policies Facing Covid 19 in Supporting Nonmilitary Defense. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*, 04(04). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v4-i4-11>
- [17] Subekti, M., Faozanudin, M., & Rokhman Ali. (2017). The influence of communication, resources, disposition and bureaucratic structure on the effectiveness of the implementation of school operational assistance programs in public elementary school education units in Tambak sub-district. *The Indonesian Journal of Public Administration (IJPA)*, 3(2), 58–71.
- [18] Sudirman, I. (2021). Analysis of the Public Policy Formation Process: A Case Study of the Karawang Cerdas Scholarship Program in 2020. In *Indonesian Journal of Social and Political Sciences* (Vol. 2, Issue 1).
- [19] Untari, D. (2018). The Role of Sari Husada Product Marketing Administration of PT Tigaraksa Satria Tbk Bandung Branch (Vol. 7, Issue 2).